

The need of using a Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) System

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ABSTRACT

The Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), is a wireless technology system that is used for identifying an individual or objects through the means of radio waves which transfer information from an electronic tag, called Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tag. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) consists of two main components the interrogator and the transponder. The Interrogator, which is the Radio Frequency identification reader (RFID Reader), the Interrogator usually transmits and receives the signal while the Transponder (tag) is attached to the object. In the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) system, an RFID reader interrogates the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags. This tag reader generates a radio frequency interrogation, which communicates with the tags been registered in the system. This reader likewise has a receiver that captures a reply signal generated from the tags and decodes the signal. This reply signal from the tags reflects the tag's information content. Each tag of the students consists of a unique identity, identification card (ID) that is assigned to a single student identification card (ID) which is recorded in the database. The use of the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology enables the institution authorities or management to evade attendance documents from damages such as misplacement, tear, or even got lost. This research review some recent design and implementation of internet of things (IoT) attendance system using the concept of the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) system articles. The analysis found that the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) system is a very advanced technology for an automatic attendance system in an institution, organization, or university and it provides a very higher performance and accuracy than the traditional paper-based system that the students normally used to sign. A combination of the model is needed which will confirm higher security, better performance, and consistency of the system.

KEYWORDS: Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) system, Radio frequency Identification (RFID) tags, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) readers, Microcontroller, Liquid Crystal Display (LCD), and Personal computer.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology, is an emergent technology that is used in a wide range of applications, it is a member of the family of Automatic Identification and Data Capture which is referred to as (AIDC) technologies. This is the fastest and reliable means or method of identifying an object or thing. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) consists of two main components the interrogator and the transponder. The Interrogator, which is the Radio Frequency identification reader (RFID Reader), the Interrogator usually transmits and receives the signal while the Transponder (tag) is attached to the object. In the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) system, an RFID reader interrogates the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags. This tag reader generates a radio frequency interrogation, which communicates with the tags been registered in the system. This reader likewise has a receiver that captures a reply signal generated from the tags and decodes the signal. This reply signal from the tags reflects the tag's information content. A Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tag usually consists of an antenna and a tiny microchip [1]. The Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) alone has various applications but when it is combined with an Arduino or Microcontroller it limitations magnifies more. The developments in Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology continue to produce larger memory capacities, faster processing, and wider reading ranges. They are a high tendency that the technology can replace barcode even with the expected reduction in raw materials together with economies of scale; the integrated circuit (IC) in a radio frequency (RF) tag can never be as expensive as a bar code label. Nevertheless, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) will continue to rise in its recognized places where the barcode or other optical technologies are less effective. Attendance or daily register of students

in an institution or university has turned into a vivacious assessment viewpoint in the current educational scheme in both institutions, organizations, schools, and universities. The unoriginal attendance-monitoring scheme has a few obstructions with the development of the latest technology gap. For example, giving out the everyday attendance sheet to a gigantic amount of students in a class is extremely risky and it hinders the consideration of the students in that particular class [2]. This is considered a waste of time and energy as well as a student can intentionally register students who are not present in the class in the attendance sheet. If the lecturer mistakenly loses these documents, all the important attendance records will be lost without hesitation. , the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) novelty has a great chore to carry out in the completion of the vision of connecting objects around us to the internet. These items extend from huge structures, planes, modern plants, vehicles, any sort of merchandise, and explicit pieces of a bigger framework to people, animals, plants, and even obvious body portions of them. The idea driving all this is called the Internet of Things (IoT) [3].

Radio Frequency Identification (RFID): radio frequency identification (RFID) operates by transferring and receiving a signal using Antenna and Integrated Circuit (IC). It has mainly two parts namely, the Radio frequency identification (RFID) Tag and the Radio frequency identification (RFID) Reader. The radio frequency identification (RFID) tags contain an integrated circuit (IC) and an antenna, which is used to transmit data to the radio frequency identification (RFID) reader also known as an interrogator. This reader then converts the radio waves to a more usable form of information. The data collected from the Radio frequency identification (RFID) tags is then transferred through a communications interface to a host computer system, where the information can be stored in a database and analyzed later. The figure below illustrates the information.

Figure 1: Shows the working operation of the Radio frequency identification (RFID) components

Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) Tag: The Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags called the transponder unit could be passive or active (RFID) depending on the asset type and its use. The active Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags usually contain a battery, a beacon to be charged periodically. Depending on the type and power of the antenna and noise in the surrounding environment, the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags could be read remotely from a distance of several hundred feet. In the case of Passive Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags, they derive their power while they are inside the signal range of the Reader. Since they are substantially less expensive than the active Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags, they have noticeably less read rangeability. The Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tag is an electronic tag that exchanges data with a Radio

Frequency Identification (RFID) reader through radio waves. Almost all the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) tags have mainly two parts namely, the Antenna and Integrated Circuit (IC). The antenna is used to receive radio frequency waves and the integrated circuit (IC) is used in the processing and store of information. The microchip on the Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) reader is written with whatever information the user wants it.

Figure 2: Radio frequency identification (RFID) tag

Figure 3: Radiofrequency identification tag in working mode

Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) Reader: The Radiofrequency identification reader is the brain of the Radio frequency identification (RFID) system and is necessary for any system to function. The Readers also called the interrogators, are devices that transmit and receive radio waves to communicate with Radio frequency identification (RFID) tags. The Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) reader is a device, which used to gather information from Radio frequency identification (RFID). The Radiofrequency identification reader (RFID) uses radio waves to transfer the data from the Radio frequency identification tag to the Radiofrequency identification reader.

Figure 4: Radio frequency identification (RFID) reader

Figure 5: Radio frequency identification (RFID) reader in working mode

2 RELATED WORKS

Designed and implementation of a wireless fingerprint-based attendance system to obtain and record the attendance information using fingerprints known as biometric [4]. Designing time management and access monitoring system using a microprocessor card to monitor students and staff's movement with the data that are kept in the database for administrator reference in campus, office, or a certain area. Headmasters, Teachers, and parents could access all the information captured by this system by fully utilizing Mykad features via the Internet and intranet facilities [5]. A system that was capable to record student's attendance using interactive input, viewing students' and lecturer profiles, generating reports, and providing students timetable the system records the attendance using a barcode scanner is design [6]. In another spectrum, a radio frequency identification (RFID) technology for checking in and checking out at parking areas without the need to stop the cars and it avoids traffic jams during the parking hours. This type of system is usually used in identifying vehicles through internet facilities by comparing the previous data in the database [7]. A system called the Radio frequency identification (RFID) Based Automatic Attendance system was developed. The

attendance system software is developed using visual basic VB.net and database (Microsoft Access). Each of the students has the Radio frequency identification (RFID) tag attached with the Student identification (ID) card. There is a serial connection between the computer and the Radio frequency identification (RFID) reader and the computer system. The Radiofrequency identification (RFID) reader is placed at the lecture hall door. Whenever students enter the lecture hall the Radio frequency identification (RFID) reader reads the Radio frequency identification (RFID) tag and it stores all data (Entry time, Name, etc.) of students into the database via a serial connection and maintains the system. Here the admin of this system can view all the documents using the software interface by retrieving the data from the database without any hitches, not like the traditional system of writing names on the attendance sheet or piece of paper [8]. Design and implemented an attendance system with the combination of Radio frequency identification (RFID) and a Web-Based system. This system uses the Radio frequency identification (RFID) tag and the Radiofrequency identification reader for getting the student's attendance and read the particulars of the students. Then this reader connects with Arduino or microcontroller which serves as the brain of the whole research because all instruction is given from there, which then passes the Radio frequency identification (RFID) reader response to the web server by the use of Arduino shield, finally, the attendance of students can be stored in web server by using PHP and MySQL. The admin of the implemented system can now view all the student's documents by login into this particular web-based application and can view all the student's details registered or stored using liquid crystal display (LCD) [9]. A system that, the Radio frequency identification (RFID) and Pose Invariant Face Verification for an automatic attendance system. The system works under two-factor verifications. In the first step, the students need to use the Radio frequency identification (RFID) tag that is read by the Radio frequency identification (RFID) reader. If the first step is succeeded then it moves to the second step of verification, if not, the student becomes under the unrecognized category. The second step is Face verification, if the face match with the

particular registered in the Radio frequency identification (RFID) tag then it marks the student attendance that is in the database. Missing the above readings, the system will automatically identify the fraud students. This two-factor automatic system reduces the misuse of identity theft for getting attendance because they are not registered in the system database [10]. A Student Attendance Management System Based on Radio frequency identification (RFID) and Fingerprint Reader. The system also works as a two-factor verification system. In the system, the Radio frequency identification (RFID) reader is linked with the computer and the computer has specific software that is used to measure the automatic attendance of the students which is developed by Microsoft Visual basic studio and SQL. In the first place, the entire student must register his or her Radio frequency identification (RFID) tag and Fingerprints and it is stored in the database of the system. Once the students enter the classroom they need to use the Radio frequency identification (RFID) tag and this will be read by the Radio frequency identification (RFID) reader which will then check the database of the system to check if the tag is registered, if it is registered or correct then he moves to the next verification step. In the second step, the fingerprint of the student is then verified. If it matched the information of the students registered he or her then the attendance of the student will be stored on the server. Besides, the lecturers or teachers have authentication to use the system, they can also act as admin of the entire system [11]. An SD card module with the Radio frequency identification (RFID) tag, which carries different voice codes, is used in the system development. The tag identification card (ID) and the code of the voice greeting are stored in the SD card module. When the student enters the classroom door, his or her Radio frequency identification (RFID) tag is being read. If the identification card (ID) of the student tag matched with the stored data in the SD card then the particulars of the student or person needs to use the voice greeting, if it matches then the door will be open and the attendance of the student will be store in the excel sheet. The Student can view their attendance detail using the liquid crystal display (LCD) use in the research. In the research, the Arduino or microcontroller, connects the liquid

crystal display (LCD), the Radio frequency identification (RFID) reader, the SD card module, and the rest components use in the research. Likewise, the system has very simple schematics than another system because of the very simple components use and the design of the whole system. Also, you can we get fast response and accurate results [12]. A model system called the Microcontroller Based Attendance System Using the radio frequency identification (RFID) system and Global System for Mobile (GSM) was design. The system consists of three atMega16microcontroller placed in between the radio frequency identification (RFID) reader, Global System for Mobile (GSM) modem, and the computer. Each of the microcontrollers uses has its purpose. The system will starts whenever a lecturer or teacher used his or her radio frequency identification (RFID) tag to enter the lecture room or classroom then the students will enter the classroom also by swapping their radio frequency identification (RFID) tags within five minutes. The radio frequency identification (RFID) reader reads the radio frequency identification (RFID) tag, sends the signal to the first microcontroller, which will analyze the signal of the radio frequency identification (RFID) reader, and opens the classroom door using infrared rays (IR) signal, which is influence by a motor. This signal is temporarily stored in the microcontroller, when the lecturer or teacher finishes his or her class he or she must swap the radio frequency identification (RFID) tag again to the radio frequency identification reader and the system will decide automatically that the class is finished. Therefore, the microcontroller will pass the temporarily stored signal to the computer database as the attendance. In case if a student is absent, the signal will pass it to the global system for mobile, (GSM) modem and it will send this message to the parents of the students who were not present during the lectures or lesson in the lecture room or the classroom. If any of the students go out before the lecturer or teacher, the system will not count the student present in the lecture room or classroom. The system itself is an added advantage and a reliable security system. Thus, the students cannot cheat the administration and their parents [13]. A system that will work with the radio frequency

identification (RFID) and global system for mobile (GSM). In their research, they used a microcontroller as a midway among global systems for mobile (GSM) module and the radio frequency (RFID). Whenever the students enter the lecture room or classroom, they need to make use of their tag, which is read by the radio frequency (RFID) reader, and it sends it to the global system for mobile (GSM) module. If the identification card (ID) of the student or individual tag does not match with the stored information of the database he or she is considered as an unapproved person. If it accepts the tag, then the global system for mobile (GSM) module will send a message to the administration and their parents that the students attended lectures or lessons [14]. A system that uses web-based attendance using four-tier architecture by the use of radio frequency identification (RFID) and Biometrics. In their system, the students, lecturers, or teachers' radio frequency identification (RFID) has a unique code, which will be store in the database of the institution or school. The radiofrequency reader (RFID) reader and the fingerprint device are placed at the entrance door of the lecture room or classroom. Whenever the students want to enter the classroom, they need to use the radio frequency identification (RFID) tag which will be read by a radio frequency identification (RFID) reader and validates the identity of the students by comparing it with the information store in the database whether the tag matches or not. The second stage of verification will be allowed if and only if the first stage of verification is succeeded. The Verification with the fingerprint is the second stage of the system and if the student's fingerprint matches with the data in the database then the attendance will be marked and stored into the database, but if he or her record does not store or capture in the database then they will be no attendance for that student. The fingerprint verification is merely acting in ten minutes including five minutes before the schedule and after the schedule of class starting time. If anyone is late then it will deny providing attendance to that particular student that is late but the students can stay at the lectures and learn but will not have attendance for that class. Lastly, a short message service (SMS) will be sent to the students' parents if the students are present or not in the lecture room or classroom

[15]. Prototype of the attendance management system with the placement of a bigger number of radio frequency identification (RFID) readers placed in the room and there is a server application maintains through a laptop. The radio frequency identification reader and the laptop or personal computer (PC) are connected with the help of a wireless router or LAN connection. Whenever a student or person enters the classroom or lecture room, he or she needs to use the radio frequency identification (RFID) tag which is read by the radio frequency identification (RFID) reader and passes the student's attendance to the server through wireless or LAN connection. Since many of the radio frequency identification (RFID) readers are placed, more than one person can get the attendance simultaneously and get the higher efficiency than the traditional method or using the single radio frequency identification reader [16]. In addition, proposed a system that is working with the radio frequency identification (RFID) and Telegram Messenger Application. In their system, the students need to meet their lecturers or teachers for the tapping of their radio frequency identification (RFID) tags. If the tags match with tag information stored in the database, then it will send the attendance to the management of the institution or principal in the form of an excel sheet as well as sends a message to the specific student's parent via Telegram messenger. Meanwhile, facial verification cost is comparably average to other biometric verification. It also could be considered for a better system for developing an automatic attendance system. The radio frequency identification (RFID) with fingerprint system is very comparable to the radio frequency identification (RFID) with the facial system. Each characteristic of the table is providing similar ideas except for their cost. Fingerprint biometric systems provide a very lower cost compare to Retina and Iris. Meanwhile, software, which makes use of visual studio and SQL, are costs in a great measure. Eventually, the system is considered a high-cost system with a higher eminence [17]. Low-Cost Portable Smart Card Based Attendance System. Is the combination of frequency Identification (RFID) with fingerprint biometric technology to enhance the safety level and integrity of the records. This design system does not merely make the system

design simpler but likewise improves the efficiency of the institution both in terms of manpower and time. This system does not merely abridge the method of taking attendance but decreases the rate of errors and permits for faster verification of student attendance, all with minimal human interaction [18]. Smart Attendance Monitoring System (SAMS) A Face Recognition based Attendance System for Classroom Environment. This system is developed by the integration of omnipresent components to make a portable device for managing the student's attendance using Face Recognition technology [19]. A Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) Based Attendance System with Short Message Service (SMS) Backup. This project seeks to address means of automatically registering the students recording attendance, saving students information on the personal computer (PC) as well as backing their information via the global system for mobile communication (GSM), and finally making a decision on the worthiness of a student to sit for an examination course or attending the lectures [20].

3. III. The need of using a radio frequency identification (rfid) system over the traditional paper-based attendance system and its various places of applications

1. Radio frequency identification (RFID) can be used in various environments, this includes livestock, military, and scientific areas, and also in tertiary institutions to prevent unnecessary intrusions by the students.
2. Radio frequency identification (RFID) can be used in addition to Barcode. These two technologies can be complementing each other. With the combinations of such technologies, one can hardly enter secure environments or institutions.
3. Unattended operations are possible, minimizing human errors and high costs.
4. Radio frequency identification (RFID) can help in identifying moving objects or elements that have tags embedded in them.
5. Radio frequency identification (RFID). can cover a larger area of coverage, Up to several feet.
6. It is used for access management the radio frequency identification system.

7. The radio frequency identification (RFID) system is use in the tracking of goods.
8. radio frequency identification (RFID) is used in the tracking of persons and animals.
9. radio frequency identification (RFID) is used in Tax collection and contactless payment
10. The radio frequency identification (RFID) system is used as a machine in reading travel documents.
11. radio frequency identification (RFID) is used in airport Baggage Tracking Logistics.
12. radio frequency identification (RFID) is used in passports development.
13. radio frequency identification (RFID) is used for medicine and drugs record.
14. radio frequency identification (RFID) tags are used in clothing, e.g. in Jeans, shirts, coats, and trousers, etc.

4 CONCLUSION

In this paper, I have reviewed many papers related to the radio frequency identification (RFID) system we have seen their various improvements in technologies and the need of using the radio frequency identification (RFID) system over the traditional paper-based attendance sheet, which has been used over several years, and its various places of applications.

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